

Energy Transfer between CNT Surface and $-\text{Re}(\text{CO})_3(\text{phen})^{+*}$ Pendants Grafted to P4VP in Nanohybrid Shish-Kebab-like Structures

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Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: The adsorption of a $\text{Re}(\text{CO})_3(\text{phen})$ -poly(4-vinylpyridine) polymer, RePVP, on multiwall carbon nanotubes surfaces is studied by transmission electron microscopy and absorption spectroscopy in combination with chemometric techniques in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture. Nanohybrid structures like a shish-kebab (NHSK) are observed by TEM when RePVP is wrapped around carbon nanotubes (CNTs) surfaces. The association between RePVP and CNTs studied by absorption spectroscopy suggests the coexistence of CNTs with a high or low content of adsorbed RePVP on their surface. In the absence of CNTs, the photophysical properties of RePVP (i.e., luminescence quantum yield, Φ_L , and amplitude-weighted average lifetimes, $\langle\tau\rangle$) are strongly dependent on the morphology of the polymer as witnessed by the dependence of Φ_L on the concentration of RePVP (C_{RePVP}) and the fact that in CH₃CN Φ_L and $\langle\tau\rangle$ are sensitive to O₂ while in a MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture they are not. In the NHSK, an energy-transfer process between excited $-\text{Re}(\text{CO})_3(\text{phen})^{+*}$ pendent chromophores and the CNTs surface, with static and dynamic components, is responsible for the quenching of the RePVP luminescence by CNTs.

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), they have received great attention due to their extraordinary mechanical, electrical, and optical properties.¹ Nevertheless, difficulties that arose from their low solubility and poor processability hindered their chemical manipulations thus limiting their further use and applications.^{2–4} As a result, the functionalization of CNTs became imperative. In response to this, two strategies were developed: (i) chemical functionalization techniques and (ii) noncovalent wrapping methods.¹ Within the latter, nanocomposites formed by the wrapping of polymers around CNTs surfaces belong to the most promising fields for CNTs.⁵ The enhancement of conductivity, electrostatic dissipation, and the fabrication of aerospace structural materials stand up as potential applications of these polymer/CNT nanocomposites.⁵ Thus, a variety of polymers able to form nanocomposites with CNTs have been studied depend-

ing on the property sought after. Taking into consideration their excellent mechanical properties, crystalline polymers are regarded as ideal partners for wrapping CNTs and preparing polymer/CNT nanocomposites.⁵ By this method, the structural integrity of CNTs can be retained, and simultaneously the disability of the noncovalent modification method can be overcome.⁶

As transition metals can coordinate pyridine groups of poly(4-vinylpyridine) (P4VP), the latter is widely studied for applications in catalysis, in humidity-sensing, and as an antimicrobial material.⁵ Moreover, besides being a cationic polyelectrolyte in the water at pH < 5 as well as a hydrophobic polymer in apolar solvents,^{7,8} P4VP can be easily quaternized

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to form positively charged polyelectrolytes which may further be utilized as sensors and actuators.^{9,10} It is then not surprising that in recent years the wrapping of P4VP around CNTs for obtaining polymer/CNT nanocomposites has been studied.^{5,11} As functionalization of CNT is growing popular in nanotechnology, the P4VP/CNT nanocomposite is expected to play a vital role in exploring and developing the potential applications of the corresponding polymer/CNT nanocomposites.⁵

Polymers containing transition metal chromophores have been prepared where group phenomena such as fast, site-to-site energy-transfer hopping and photochemically induced electron transfer have been observed.¹² In the last two decades, we have focused our research interests on the study of the photochemical and morphological properties of Re(I) polymeric complexes. The polymers used in our works have been derived from the P4VP backbone, and they contain *fac*-XRe(CO)₃L pendants in their structure.^{13–24} The Re(I) polymers are polyelectrolytes where Re(I) center coordinates one of every three pyridines present in the P4VP. They display interesting as well as intriguing features both in photochemistry and in material science.

From the nanoscience standpoint, Re(I) polymers showed the formation of nanoaggregated structures where the association of several hundreds of polymer strands occurred in nearly spherical aggregates.^{15,17,19} Multiple morphologies of those polymer aggregates were obtained by using different solvents.¹⁵ The photophysical and photochemical properties of these polymers showed a markedly distinct behavior when they were compared to those of the single *fac*-XRe(CO)₃L units.^{20,22,25} Moreover, linking the photochemistry and nanoscience realm, the ³MLCT luminescence quenching by amines in single [Re(CO)₃L]⁺ molecules and Re(I) polymeric systems showed significant differences. For instance, the observed rate constants for the quenching of the ³MLCT luminescence of a P4VP polymer containing pendent $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{bpy})\text{]}^+$ chromophores by amines shows “vestiges” of the inverted effect predicted by Marcus while the quenching of [pyRe(CO)₃(bpy)]⁺ luminescence follows a Rehm–Weller type of behavior.¹⁴ Lately, we found that a correlation exists between photophysical properties and morphological changes of the polymer backbone.²³ These transformations, i.e., concentration-dependent morphologies revealed by TEM and AFM morphological studies, are responsible for a significant increase of the MLCT_{Re(I)→phen} excited state luminescence lifetime when the polymer concentration is increased.²³

In this paper, we study the association of RePVP (see Scheme 1) to the surface of multiwall CNTs, MWCNTs, in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture by absorption spectroscopy, chemometric techniques, and transmission electron microscopy. A nanohybrid structure like a shish-kebab was observed as a result of the wrapping of RePVP around the MWCNT surface. The photophysical properties of both RePVP and RePVP/CNT nanocomposites were studied by steady-state and time-resolved photoluminescence spectroscopy. The photophysical properties of the polymer RePVP were studied both in CH₃CN and in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture. In both solvents, Φ_L and ⟨τ⟩ increase with the rise of the polymer concentration due to morphology changes that affect the photophysical properties. The quenching of the luminescence of RePVP by molecular oxygen which occurs in CH₃CN was not observed in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture. The fact that Φ_L and ⟨τ⟩ are dependent on O₂ concentration in CH₃CN, which

Scheme 1. Schematic Representation of the Structure of RePVP Alone

is not observed in MeOH/H₂O, suggests that in the latter solvent mixture more compact polymer structures are achieved than in CH₃CN, yielding polymer regions that are inaccessible for oxygen. When the luminescence of RePVP/CNT nanocomposites was compared to that of RePVP, it was found that the increase of Φ_L and ⟨τ⟩ with the rise of RePVP concentration was less significant in RePVP/CNT nanocomposites than for RePVP alone due to the quenching of the luminescence of RePVP by the nanotube surface in the nanocomposite. The quenching of the luminescence of RePVP by the surface of MWCNTs occurred by an energy-transfer process that showed both static and dynamic behavior in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. The rhenium(I) polymer, RePVP, was available from previous work.²⁰ Oxidized multiwall carbon nanotubes, oxCNT, were obtained from commercial MWCNT, here denoted as pCNT. pCNT were Nanocyl™ NC7000 Industrial grade, C purity 90%, diameter 9.5 nm, length 1.5 mm, specific surface area 475 m² g⁻¹. The following is the published content of main impurities determined by EDX analysis: Al (5.9 wt %), Fe (0.5 wt %), and Co (0.2 wt %).²⁶ After purification (i.e., mainly metal extraction) of pCNT by treatment with 12 M HCl acid, they were oxidized with concentrated H₂SO₄/HNO₃ acids mixture following literature procedures²⁷ to obtain the desired oxCNT. After oxidation, treatment with NaOH 0.05 M allowed neutralization of carboxylic acids present in the oxCNT to form carboxylate anions in the oxCNT.²⁷ With this method, two oxidized MWCNT were accessible: oxCNTa and oxCNTb. In oxCNTa, the carboxylic acid groups present in oxCNT were not submitted to NaOH treatment while in oxCNTb the carboxylic acid moieties present in oxCNT were converted to carboxylate anions by treatment with NaOH. FTIR spectra of oxCNTa and oxCNTb showed the signature features of COOH and COO⁻, respectively, present in the structure of oxCNT (see Scheme 2). The association between the RePVP and oxCNTa was studied in the solvent mixture MeOH/H₂O (1:9 v–v).

Photophysical Measurements. Absorption spectra were measured on a Varian Cary 5000 double-beam UV–vis–NIR spectrometer and baseline-corrected. Steady-state excitation

Scheme 2. Schematic Representation of the Procedure To Obtain oxCNTa and oxCNTb

and emission spectra were recorded on a FluoTime300 spectrometer from PicoQuant equipped with a 300 W ozone-free Xe lamp (250–900 nm), a 10 W Xe flash-lamp (250–900 nm, pulse width $<10 \mu\text{s}$) with repetition rates of 0.1–300 Hz, an excitation monochromator (Czerny-Turner 2.7 nm/mm dispersion, 1200 grooves/mm, blazed at 300 nm), diode lasers (pulse width $<80 \text{ ps}$) operated by a computer-controlled laser driver PDL-820 (repetition rate up to 80 MHz, burst mode for slow and weak decays), two emission monochromators (Czerny-Turner, selectable gratings blazed at 500 nm with 2.7 nm/mm dispersion and 1200 grooves/mm or blazed at 1250 nm with 5.4 nm/mm dispersion and 600 grooves/mm), Glan-Thompson polarizers for excitation (Xe lamps) and emission, a Peltier-thermostatized sample holder from Quantum Northwest (-40 to $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), and two detectors, namely, a PMA Hybrid 40 (transit time spread fwhm $<120 \text{ ps}$, 300–720 nm) and an R5509-42 NIR-photomultiplier tube (transit time spread fwhm 1.5 ns, 300–1400 nm) with external cooling ($-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) from Hamamatsu. Steady-state and fluorescence lifetimes were recorded in TCSPC mode by a PicoHarp 300 (minimum base resolution 4 ps). Emission and excitation spectra were corrected for source intensity (lamp and grating) by standard correction curves. Lifetime analysis was performed using commercial FluoFit software. The quality of the fit was assessed by minimizing the reduced chi-squared function (χ^2) and visual inspection of the weighted residuals and their autocorrelation. Luminescence quantum yields were measured with a Hamamatsu Photonics absolute PL quantum yield measurement system (C9920-02) equipped with an L9799-01 CW Xenon light source (150 W), monochromator, C7473 photonic multichannel analyzer, and integrating sphere and employing U6039-05 PLQY measurement software (Hamamatsu Photonics, Ltd., Shizuoka, Japan). The uncertainty for the quantum yields measured with this equipment is (± 0.02). All solvents used were of spectrometric grade.

Transient absorption spectra were performed by excitation with the third harmonic of an Nd:YAG Continuum Surelite laser (2 ns full width at half-maximum (fwhm) and 6 mJ/pulse at 355 nm). The detection system was that of the Edinburgh FP980.

Association Studies and Spectroscopic Analysis. The association between the RePVP and oxCNTa was studied by following the spectral changes between 200 and 800 nm after

well-mixing a known volume of a MeOH/H₂O (1:9 v–v) stock solution of RePVP and a known volume of a stock dispersion of oxCNTa in the same solvent mixture. After mixture, the solutions were sonicated for 30 min. In these experiments, the concentration of RePVP was varied from 10 to 80 ppm and those of oxCNTa between 0.5 and 20 ppm. In one type of experiment, the concentration of RePVP was kept constant at 30 ppm, and the concentration of oxCNTa was varied between 0.5 and 20 ppm. In another type of experiment, the concentration of oxCNTa was kept constant at 3 ppm, and the concentration of RePVP was varied between 10 and 80 ppm. The resulting dispersions were kept still in the dark for at least 24 h to allow full equilibration and interaction prior to absorbance measurements.

An extended multiplicative signal correction (EMSC) preprocessing method²⁸ as implemented in the Unscrambler-X program allowed a separation of physical light-scattering effects from chemical light absorbance effects in spectra form. After the EMSC pretreatment of UV–vis absorption data, we used chemometric techniques in order to retrieve, from the absorbance matrix, the concentration profiles and the spectra of each contributing species.^{29,30} These methods can be applied to bilinear spectroscopic data from a chemical reaction to provide information about composition changes in an evolving system. In the present work, we used the alternating least-squares (ALS) algorithm to simultaneously estimate concentration and spectral profiles.³¹ ALS extracts useful information from the experimental data matrix $A(i \times j)$ by the iterative application of the following matrix product: $A = CS^T + E$ where $C(i \times n)$ is the matrix of the concentrations profiles, $S^T(n \times j)$ is that containing the spectral profiles, and $E(i \times j)$ represents the error matrix. The indexes i , n , and j denote the samples, absorbing species, and recorded wavelengths, respectively. Resolving matrix A may be a rather difficult task³² since, on the one hand, n is usually unknown³³ and, on the other hand, curve resolution methods cannot deliver a single solution because of rotational and scale ambiguities.³⁴ We applied factor analysis and singular value decomposition to the experimental matrix for the estimation of n . In order to reduce rotational ambiguities, we used some chemically relevant constraints³⁵ such as non-negativity, closure, selectivity, and unimodality. The association between RePVP and oxCNTb was not studied by absorption spectroscopy techniques due to the fact that their dispersions were less stable than the dispersions formed in RePVP/oxCNTa systems. However, as well as with RePVP/oxCNTa, the interactions between RePVP and oxCNTb were ascertained by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) experiments, see below.

Transmission Electron Microscopy. TEM experiments were performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific (previously FEI) Themis G3 60-300 transmission electron microscope (TEM) equipped with a high-brightness field emission gun (X-FEG), a monochromator, an image Cs-corrector, a quadrupole energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) system (Super-X EDX detector), a high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector (Fischione Model 3000), and a fast CMOS camera (Ceta, $4k \times 4k$). For the measurements, the microscope was operated at an acceleration voltage of either 60 or 300 kV.

Dynamic Light Scattering. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements were done using a Malvern Zetasizer. Data were analyzed using ZS Xplorer 1.00 software. For the measurements, plastic $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ cuvettes were used. A

Figure 1. (a) Absorbance spectra of Sp1–Sp4. (b) Concentration profiles of Sp1–Sp4.

refractive index of 1.52 (RI of PVP) and 0.99 of absorbance were settled. The equilibration time was 120 s, and the temperature was set to 25 °C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Association between RePVP and CNTs Studied by Absorption Spectroscopy. The UV–vis spectral changes accompanying the association between the RePVP and oxCNTa are shown in Figure S1a–d. In those figures, absorption changes are due to both increase of RePVP or oxCNTa concentration as well as light-scattering increase due to the increase of oxCNTa concentration. Figure S1a–b corresponds to calibration spectra (S1a and S1b to RePVP or oxCNTa at varying concentrations, respectively). On the other hand, Figure S1c corresponds to UV–vis absorption spectra for solutions with $C_{RePVP} = 30$ ppm and $C_{oxCNTa} = 1$ –16 ppm, while in Figure S1d $C_{RePVP} = 3$ –70 ppm and $C_{oxCNTa} = 3$ ppm. Figure S2 shows the EMSC pretreatment of experimental data of Figure S1. Note that after EMSC, the experimental data of Figure S1c–d, which originally correspond to very different scales in the y -axis, can be plotted in the same graph (Figure S2c). Moreover, subtle spectral changes that can be clearly observed in Figure S2c were obscured in Figure S1c–d due to additive and multiplicative light-scattering effects. The spectral profiles of Figure S2c were subjected to chemometric techniques in order to retrieve, from the absorbance matrix, the concentration profiles and the spectra of each contributing species. Figure 1 shows the spectral and the concentration profiles retrieved from the chemometric analysis of absorbance changes in Figure S2c.

Four species, Sp1–Sp4, were needed to reproduce the spectral changes in Figure S2c, whose spectra are shown in Figure 1a. Figure 1b shows the relative concentrations (C_{rel}) of those species as a function of either RePVP or oxCNTa concentration. Two different types of experiments are gathered in Figure 1. In one type of experiment, C_{RePVP} is kept constant at $C_{RePVP} = 30$ ppm, and C_{oxCNTa} is varied between 1 and 16 ppm. In another type of experiment, $C_{oxCNTa} = 3$ ppm, and the concentration of RePVP is varied between 3 and 70 ppm. In Figure 1b, $C_{rel}(1, 2)$ are plotted against C_{oxCNTa} (bottom x -axis) while $C_{rel}(3, 4)$ are plotted against C_{RePVP} (top x -axis). Sp1 and

Sp2 represent oxCNTa with a high or low content of adsorbed RePVP on their surface, respectively. The spectra of Sp3 and Sp4 are intermediate between those of Sp1 and Sp2. In the experiments where $C_{RePVP} = 30$ ppm and C_{oxCNTa} was varied from 1 to 16 ppm, it can be observed that $C_{Sp1} \sim C_{Sp2}$ ($C_{rel} \sim 0.5$) when $C_{oxCNTa} \sim 5$ ppm. This implies that there are about ~ 2200 C atoms in the oxCNTa surface for each adsorbed RePVP polymer. A similar number can be obtained from the dependence of Sp3 and Sp4 on C_{RePVP} at constant (3 ppm) C_{oxCNTa} .

Association between RePVP and CNTs Studied by TEM. Figure 2 and Figure S3 shows TEM images of MeOH/

Figure 2. TEM images of RePVP on a holey carbon film.

H₂O cast films of RePVP on holey carbon film grids. RePVP polymers aggregate into spherical and/or ovoid shapes of around 25 nm average diameters. Small dots at polymer-like scales, i.e., less than 7 nm,¹⁷ can be discerned within those aggregates. Some representative regions including those aggregates were observed with the high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector, and their atomic constituents (C, N, O, S, F, Re) were mapped by the energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) system. Figure 3 shows a HAADF image and

Figure 3. HAADF image and corresponding EDX maps of RePVP aggregates on a holey carbon film. HAADF (gray), rhenium (green), fluorine (yellow), sulfur (cyan), oxygen (magenta), and nitrogen (blue).

corresponding EDX maps for those RePVP polymer aggregates. The same aggregates imaged by the HAADF detector are those where the characteristic X-ray emissions of atoms are detected by EDX indicating clearly the presence of Re, S, F, and O in the pendent $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})\text{]}^+$ (plus counterion CF_3SO_3^-) attached to the backbone of P4VP.

Figure 4 and Figure S4 shows HRTEM images of MeOH/H₂O cast films of oxCNT where long intertwined noodle-like structures of CNTs at micrometer length scales are in coexistence with shorter ones at $\sim 100\text{--}400$ nm lengths.

Figure 4. HRTEM images of the (a) oxCNTa and (b) oxCNTb on a holey carbon film.

At this point, it is noteworthy to mention a precedent to this work where the functionalization of MWCNTs with crystalline P4VP in CO₂-expanded liquids (CXLs) was studied.¹¹ In that paper, the structure and morphology of P4VP adsorbed over the MWCNT surface were examined, and it was found that the wrapping patterns of P4VP around MWCNT undergo a morphological evolution from dot crystals to dotted helical wrappings and then to dense helical patterns depending on the different experimental conditions.¹¹

–RePVP with oxCNTa. Figures 5 and S5 show HRTEM along with HAADF images of MeOH/H₂O cast films

Figure 5. HRTEM and HAADF images of cast films containing both RePVP (5 ppm) and oxCNTa (2 ppm), partly on a holey carbon film, partly spanning the holes in the film.

containing both RePVP (5 ppm) and oxCNTa (2 ppm). Our results suggest that in the RePVP/oxCNTa system, dense helical structures are formed when the wrapping of RePVP around oxCNTa occurs.

EDX maps in Figure 6 confirmed the presence of Re, S, F, and O in the pendent $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})\text{]}^+$ (plus counterion CF_3SO_3^-) in the surface of the oxCNTa. A nanohybrid structure like a shish-kebab (NHSK) is observed from the HAADF image: the oxCNTa are forming the central shish while round-shaped RePVPs are wrapped along the MWCNTs stems constituting the kebab. RePVP crystal kebab, which are roughly round-shaped, can be regarded as periodically perpendicular to the stem axis. Typical NHSK structures have been reported in the literature.^{1,5,6,36} It has to be noted that Re appears to be present also in the empty spaces between the CNTs array, indicating that at the concentration used in TEM experiments, $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 5$ ppm and $C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 2$ ppm, the RePVP is in excess relative to oxCNTa and the CNTs surface is saturated by RePVP.

Figures S6 and S7 show similar behavior for the wrapping of RePVP over oxCNTb surface in HRTEM and HAADF images as well as in EDX maps. The adsorption of RePVP over oxCNTa surfaces was studied also at higher concentrations of both polymer and CNT than those illustrated before in Figures

Figure 6. HAADF image and corresponding EDX maps of the NHSK structure spanning a hole in a carbon film. The color code is the same as in Figure 3. HAADF (gray), rhenium (green), fluorine (yellow), sulfur (cyan), oxygen (magenta), and nitrogen (blue).

2–6 and S4–S7. To this end we repeated TEM measurements with $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 25$ ppm and $C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 10$ ppm. Figures 7–8 and S8–S9 shows the respective TEM data.

Figure 7. HRTEM and HAADF images with $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 25$ ppm and $C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 10$ ppm.

It is observed that in addition to the NHSK, some isolated and larger spherical shapes than the kebab part of the NHSK are present, Figure 8. In some cases, those spheres can be about 600 nm in diameter. Those spheres constitute nanoaggregates of RePVP, which are not part of the NHSK but are still in contact with the oxCNTa surfaces. These kinds of RePVP nanoaggregates have already been observed before in morphology studies of Re(I) polymers. In fact, Re(I) polymers derived from P4VP showed the formation of nanoaggregated structures where the association of several hundreds of polymer strands occurred in nearly spherical aggregates.^{15,17,19} In addition, multiple morphologies of those polymers aggregates were obtained by using different solvents.¹⁵

–**RePVP with oxCNTb.** Figures 9 and S10 show TEM images for the adsorption of RePVP over oxCNTb with similar

Figure 8. HAADF image and corresponding EDX maps of the spherical nanoaggregates. HAADF (gray), rhenium (green), fluorine (yellow), sulfur (cyan), oxygen (magenta), and nitrogen (blue).

experimental conditions to those utilized for samples illustrated in Figures. 7–8 and S6–S7. In the case of adsorption over oxCNTb surfaces, the coexistence of the spherical nanoaggregates of RePVP with the NHSK was not observed. In fact, the NHSK structure over oxCNTb is somewhat different from that observed with oxCNTa. In the case of the NHSK structure over oxCNTb, the presence of dots can be discerned, which were not observed in NHSK over oxCNTa structures. In addition, over the oxCNTb surfaces, the kebab parts are not as round-shaped as those in oxCNTa with some disklike or starlike structures which can be distinguished.

Dynamic Light Scattering. Solutions of RePVP in MeOH/H₂O at polymer concentration of 10 ppm $< C_{\text{RePVP}} < 100$ ppm display a bimodal spectrum of polymer sizes. Two mean diameters of polymer aggregates were observed: one around $d \sim 200$ nm and another with $d \sim 400$ nm. When the concentration of RePVP is 10 ppm $< C_{\text{RePVP}} < 25$ ppm, the polymer aggregates with $d \sim 200$ nm prevail with more than a 99% contribution to the total scattered light. On the other hand, when $C_{\text{RePVP}} > 25$ ppm, the aggregates with $d \sim 200$ nm contribute to $\sim 93\%$ of the total scattered light while the contribution of the larger aggregates is around 7% (Figure S11).

Figure 9. HRTEM and HAADF images of RePVP over oxCNTb.

Photophysical Properties of RePVP Polymers in MeOH/H₂O. A broad unstructured band centered at $\lambda \sim 550$ nm is observed in the emission spectrum of RePVP when a deaerated solution of the polymer in CH₃CN is irradiated at 350 nm.^{20,24} A similar luminescence of the Re(I) chromophores is observed in MeOH/H₂O mixtures, which can be attributed to the relaxation of the ³MLCT excited state of the pendent $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^+$ in RePVP. Luminescence quantum yields of RePVP, Φ_L , were measured under different experimental conditions, see Table 1. It can be observed that

Table 1. Luminescence Quantum Yields, Φ_L , and Amplitude-Weighted Average Lifetimes, $\langle\tau\rangle$, of RePVP Measured under Different Experimental Conditions

$C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}$	Φ_L (Ar)	Φ_L (air)	$C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}$	$\langle\tau\rangle/\mu\text{s}$ (Ar)	$\langle\tau\rangle/\mu\text{s}$ (air)
CH ₃ CN					
100	0.08	0.03	100	0.780	0.224
50	0.05	0.02	50	0.540	0.179
25	0.03	0.01	25	0.341	0.111
MeOH/H ₂ O					
100	0.20	0.19	100	1.360	1.319
54	0.12	0.13	50	1.311	1.286
27	0.11	0.11	25	1.226	1.245
18	0.09	0.10	16.7	1.165	1.156
13.5	0.08	0.08	12.5	1.198	1.204
10.8	0.06	0.07	10	1.012	0.998

both in CH₃CN or in MeOH/H₂O mixtures Φ_L increases when RePVP concentration is increased. In CH₃CN, in addition, Φ_L increases substantially when the aerated solutions are degassed with Ar. This effect of O₂ on Φ_L was not observed in MeOH/H₂O mixtures where almost the same values of Φ_L were obtained under either Ar or air atmosphere.

Varying the concentration of RePVP in the range 10 ppm < $C_{\text{RePVP}} < 120$ ppm, the following linear dependences for the increase of Φ_L with C_{RePVP} were obtained:

$$\Phi_L(\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{air}) = 0.065 + 0.00125(C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}) \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi_L(\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{Ar}) = 0.059 + 0.00138(C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}) \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi_L(\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, \text{Ar}) = 0.0145 + 0.000666(C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}) \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi_L(\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, \text{air}) = 0.0075 + 0.000226(C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}) \quad (4)$$

The luminescence decays, either in CH₃CN or in MeOH/H₂O mixtures, could only be fitted by a sum of at least two or even in some cases three exponentials. This experimental observation is due to either or both different morphologies of the strand's aggregates and different environments of the pendants. Amplitude-weighted average lifetimes, $\langle\tau\rangle = \sum a_i \tau_i / \sum a_i$ were calculated from the fitted luminescence decays with lifetimes τ_i and amplitudes a_i , respectively. In CH₃CN, $\langle\tau\rangle$ were higher for Ar deaerated solutions than for aerated solutions, showing a similar trend as that observed for Φ_L . In MeOH/H₂O mixtures, $\langle\tau\rangle$ were the same, within experimental uncertainty, when solutions were exposed to atmospheric air or when they were deaerated with Ar. $\langle\tau\rangle$ increases when C_{RePVP} increases in a similar way as that observed for the increase of Φ_L with increasing C_{RePVP} . Figure 10 shows the relationship between Φ_L and $\langle\tau\rangle$ for all the experimental conditions.

Figure 10. Dependence of Φ_L vs $\langle\tau\rangle$ in CH₃CN or in MeOH/H₂O mixtures. Φ_L and $\langle\tau\rangle$ were measured in Ar-purged or air-equilibrated solutions. The numbers indicate C_{RePVP} in ppm. See the text for details.

It is clear from that figure that even using $\langle\tau\rangle$, the linear relationship $\Phi_L = k_f \tau$, valid only for a single fluorophore, holds in CH₃CN for RePVP up to $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 100$ ppm. Taking into account the linear relationship between Φ_L and $\langle\tau\rangle$ in CH₃CN, a mean value for k_f $\langle k_f \rangle = 9.6 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$, can be calculated in that solvent. In MeOH/H₂O, however, there is a linear relationship between Φ_L and $\langle\tau\rangle$ only up to $C_{\text{RePVP}} \sim 30$ ppm. At $C_{\text{RePVP}} > 30$ ppm there is an abrupt change in the slope. Φ_L dependences on C_{RePVP} like those of eqs 1–4 are manifestations of the effect of polymers morphological changes on the photophysical properties of the Re(I) chromophores.²⁴

The photophysical observations may be interpreted therefore in terms of charge-transfer excited states: medium-destabilized charge-transfer excited states, labeled ${}^3\text{MLCT}_{\text{md}}$ ²⁴ present in some chromophores within a strand of a polymer. ${}^3\text{MLCT}_{\text{md}}$ excited states may decay to the ground state, or they can transfer their excess electronic energy to other chromophores where medium-stabilized charge-transfer excited states, ${}^3\text{MLCT}_{\text{ms}}$, are produced. The coexistence of spherical and/or ovoid shapes of RePVP polymers aggregates of around 25 nm average diameters with small dots (diameters of ~ 7 nm) at polymer-like scales, seen by TEM in solutions of Re-P4VP, is consistent with the coexistence of ${}^3\text{MLCT}_{\text{md}}$ and ${}^3\text{MLCT}_{\text{ms}}$ excited states. The fact that Φ_{L} and $\langle\tau\rangle$ are dependent on O_2 concentration in CH_3CN while this effect is not observed in $\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggests that in the latter solvent mixture more compact polymer structures are achieved than in CH_3CN yielding inaccessible polymer regions to the solvent and thus to O_2 to be able to quench the luminescence. The abrupt change in the slope of Φ_{L} vs $\langle\tau\rangle$ in Figure 10 at $C_{\text{RePVP}} > 50$ ppm in $\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solvent mixture is in accordance with DLS experiments (see Table 2 and Figure S11) where there is a change of sizes distribution between 20 and 25 ppm.

Table 2. DLS Average Particle Diameter and Percentage Contribution to the Total Scattering of RePVP in $\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$

$C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}$	d_1/nm	d_2/nm
50	178 ± 40 (93%)	400 ± 3 (7%)
25	196 ± 8 (98%)	399 ± 3 (2%)
17	202 ± 5 (99%)	417 ± 5 (1%)
12.5	201 ± 6 (99%)	423 ± 6 (1%)
10	185 ± 20 (98%)	409 ± 12 (2%)

Photophysical Properties of RePVP Polymers Adsorbed on oxCNTa Surfaces. Table 3 shows the measured values of Φ_{L} and $\langle\tau\rangle$ for RePVP in the presence of increasing concentrations of oxCNTa in $\text{MeOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solvent mixture.

Two different kinds of experimental conditions are displayed in Table 3. In some experiments the concentration of RePVP is kept constant at $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 34$ ppm or $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 100$ ppm, and the concentration of oxCNTa is varied as $10 \text{ ppm} < C_{\text{CNT}} < 70$ ppm. In another type of experiment, both C_{RePVP} and C_{oxCNTa} are varied between 10 and 70 ppm but keeping the ratio

Table 3. Luminescence Quantum Yields, Φ_{L} , and Amplitude-Weighted Average Lifetimes, $\langle\tau\rangle$, of RePVP and oxCNTa Mixtures Measured under Different Experimental Conditions

$C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}$	$C_{\text{oxCNTa}}/\text{ppm}$	Φ_{L} (air)	$C_{\text{RePVP}}/\text{ppm}$	$C_{\text{oxCNTa}}/\text{ppm}$	$\langle\tau\rangle/\mu\text{s}$ (air)
100	0	0.19	100	0	1.319
100	10	0.18	100	10	1.306
100	30	0.10	100	20	1.269
34	10	0.10	100	30	1.176
34	20	0.08	100	40	1.119
56	55	0.03	100	50	1.098
28	28	0.04	100	60	1.050
19	18	0.04	50	50	1.067
14	14	0.05	25	25	1.065
			16.7	16.7	1.045
			12.5	12.5	1.031

$C_{\text{RePVP}}/C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 1$. It is observed that the luminescence of RePVP is quenched by the C_{oxCNTa} as both Φ_{L} and $\langle\tau\rangle$ decrease as C_{oxCNTa} increases. Figure 11 shows the dependence

Figure 11. Dependence of Φ_{L} as a function of C_{RePVP} in the absence of oxCNTa in comparison to Φ_{L} as a function of C_{RePVP} when $C_{\text{RePVP}}/C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 1$. Φ_{L} values were measured in air-equilibrated solutions.

of Φ_{L} as a function of C_{RePVP} in the absence of oxCNTa (i.e., corresponding to eq 1) in comparison to Φ_{L} as a function of C_{RePVP} when $C_{\text{RePVP}}/C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 1$. It is observed that in the latter $\Phi_{\text{L}} = 0.04 \pm 0.015$, i.e., Φ_{L} is independent of C_{RePVP} .

The quenching of the luminescence of RePVP is also manifested by a decrease of $\langle\tau\rangle$ as C_{oxCNTa} increases. In fact, a plot of Φ_0/Φ_{L} vs C_{oxCNTa} shows the typical behavior of static quenching (parabolic dependence on concentration) while the plot of $\langle\tau\rangle_0/\langle\tau\rangle$ is typical of dynamic quenching, see Figure 12. From $\langle\tau\rangle_0/\langle\tau\rangle$ vs C_{oxCNTa} a value of $k_{\text{q}} \sim 4 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ can be estimated for the mean bimolecular quenching constant.

In Figure 13, the dependence of $\langle\tau\rangle$ vs C_{RePVP} is compared between experiments carried out varying C_{RePVP} in the absence of oxCNTa with experiments carried out varying simultaneously C_{RePVP} and C_{oxCNTa} while keeping $C_{\text{RePVP}}/C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 1$.

Figure 12. Quenching of the luminescence of RePVP by CNTs. Φ is the luminescence quantum yield, and $\langle\tau\rangle$ is the amplitude-weighted average lifetime. Φ_0 and $\langle\tau\rangle_0$ stand for Φ and $\langle\tau\rangle$ values when $C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 0$. The plot of Φ_0/Φ vs C_{oxCNTa} shows the typical behavior of static quenching while the plot of $\langle\tau\rangle_0/\langle\tau\rangle$ vs C_{oxCNTa} is typical of dynamic quenching.

Figure 13. Comparison of the dependence of $\langle\tau\rangle$ vs C_{RePVP} between experiments carried out varying C_{RePVP} in the absence of CNTs with experiments carried out varying simultaneously C_{RePVP} and C_{CNT} while keeping $C_{\text{RePVP}}/C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 1$. See the text for details.

It is observed that in the absence of oxCNTa $\langle\tau\rangle$ is increased by 30% when C_{RePVP} increases from 10 to 100 ppm while in the presence of oxCNTa there is only a 5% increase in $\langle\tau\rangle$ for the same rise of C_{RePVP} .

Solutions of RePVP, $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 112$ ppm, in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture were flash irradiated at 355 nm. The transient absorption spectrum, recorded 50 ns after the irradiation (see Figure S12), has spectral features attributed to the ³MLCT excited state of the pendent $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^{+*}$. For measuring the transient spectrum, oscillographic traces were recorded at a given wavelength λ_{ob} , within a 300–700 nm wavelength span. They decayed according to a biexponential function in the same time range as that of the luminescence decays with similar $\langle\tau\rangle$. Solutions of RePVP, $C_{\text{RePVP}} = 112$ ppm and $C_{\text{oxCNTa}} = 6$ ppm, in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture were also flash-irradiated at 355 nm. The transient absorption spectrum of RePVP in the presence of oxCNTa was very similar to that of RePVP in the absence of CNTs (Figure S12). There were only two main significant differences: (i) ΔA at $\lambda_{\text{ob}} = 450$ nm (i.e., corresponding to the maximum in the transient spectrum) was significantly smaller for RePVP/oxCNTa mixtures than for RePVP alone, and (ii) in the 530–650 nm region, where the luminescence is also observed, there is a higher contribution of the luminescence to the transient absorption spectrum in RePVP than in RePVP/oxCNTa mixtures. Those differences between the transient spectra of RePVP and RePVP/oxCNTa mixtures are consistent with static and dynamic quenching of the RePVP luminescence by oxCNTa communicated above. Moreover, since no spectral changes corresponding to any redox species (solvated electron, oxidized Re(II)) were observed, it is assumed that the luminescence of RePVP is quenched by oxCNTa in an energy-transfer (EnT) process.

The static and dynamic quenching of RePVP by oxCNTa communicated above is in agreement with the adsorption of RePVP on oxCNTa surfaces. Chromophores near the oxCNTa surface in the NHSV will experience a static quenching as shown in typical parabolic dependence of a plot of Φ_0/Φ_L vs C_{oxCNTa} . The fact that $\langle\tau\rangle_0/\langle\tau\rangle$ shows a typical behavior of dynamic quenching points to pendants in excited states, $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^{+*}$, which are placed in the kebabs of the

NHSV at longer distances from the CNT surface than the distances between $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^{+*}$ adsorbed on the CNT surface, and the latter excited chromophores thus experience static quenching while the former ones do not. Since TEM experiments show also the coexistence of larger spherical objects of RePVP than the kebabs, $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^{+*}$ inside those “balls” will be quenched with EnT rate constants, k_{EnT} , which will be distance-dependent, and there will be a distribution of $-\text{[Re(CO)}_3(\text{phen})]^{+*}$ inside the “balls” contributing with different k_{EnT} to the observed $\langle\tau\rangle_0/\langle\tau\rangle$ vs C_{oxCNTa} dependence. Moreover, since RePVP, as suggested by absorption spectroscopy and TEM studies, is present in excess relative to CNTs, there will be RePVP polymers not adsorbed on the oxCNTa surface that may experience slow diffusion movements contributing also to the dynamic quenching observed.

CONCLUSION

Nanohybrid structures like a shish-kebab (NHSV) are observed by TEM when the Re(I)-poly(4-vinylpyridine) polymer, RePVP, is wrapped around CNTs surfaces in MeOH/H₂O solvent mixture. The association between RePVP and CNTs studied by absorption spectroscopy and resolved by chemometric techniques suggests the coexistence of CNTs with a high or low content of adsorbed RePVP in their surfaces, respectively. In the absence of CNTs, the effect of polymers' morphological changes on the photophysical properties of the Re(I) chromophores was manifested by the dependences of Φ_L on C_{RePVP} and the sensitivity to O₂ of the photophysical properties of RePVP in CH₃CN in contrast to the indifference of Φ_L and/or $\langle\tau\rangle$ values to the presence of O₂ in MeOH/H₂O media. In the NHSV, an EnT process with static and dynamic components is responsible for the quenching of the RePVP luminescence by CNTs. This EnT process may involve exciton diffusion and energy hopping between distant chromophores. Various mechanisms of intramolecular energy transfer have been proposed for organic polymers. In a mechanism, energy hopping in the strand may form pairs of excited chromophores that undergo annihilations. The process could involve excited states of the free pyridine pendants. It is also possible that energy can be transferred between remotely placed excited chromophores.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b10567>.

UV/vis spectra, additional TEM images, DLS measurements, and flash photolysis of the complex (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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